

USING INTERACTIVE MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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As the First President I.A. Karimov states: “Currently it is difficult to assess the value of a profound knowledge of foreign languages of our people for our country which is striving to take a worthy place in the world community; for our nation sees its great future in harmony and cooperation with foreign partners” It is worthwhile to state that the role of foreign languages, especially English language is becoming more and more crucial this year after our First president I.A.Karimov’s resolution on On measures to further improve foreign language learning system. According to the decree, starting from 2013/2014 school year foreign languages, mainly English, gradually throughout the country will be taught from the first year of schooling in the form of lesson-games and speaking games, continuing to learning the alphabet, reading and spelling in the second year (grade).

The National Teleradio Company, State Committee for communications, informatisation and telecommunication technologies, Agency for Press and Information of the Republic of Uzbekistan are tasked to prepare and broadcast language-learning programs, significantly increase access to international educational resources via Ziyonet educational network, promote publication of foreign language textbooks, magazines and other materials. In recent years with the development of media and computer technology, educators have begun to make use of interactive multi-media technologies to improve their teaching including language learning. This is particularly true in such English-speaking countries as Australia, USA, Canada, and the United Kingdom. Majority of the published research on the effectiveness of media and technology in language instruction is encouraging. Among other benefits, new technologies present opportunities to accomplish various instructional goals

(e.g., integrated language skills, critical thinking, and cooperative skills). They may also be responsive to different learning styles (e.g., auditory, visual, tangible). The practice of incorporating multi-media and computer technology into language instruction opens up a new horizon for teachers of English language to improve the overall quality of language instruction. The modern communicatively approach teaching prepares pupils to use foreign languages in real-life conditions. Use of interactive multimedia technologies in communicative teaching foreign language considerably raises quality of giving material of a lesson and efficiency of mastering of this material by pupils.

Records are recorded by professional sound technicians with participation of specially invited actors - of native speakers. Nowadays there is a set of multimedia tutorials, such as interactive courses “Tell me more”, “English: a way to perfection”, children’s encyclopaedias (for example: “Encyclopaedia Britannica”), etc. They are calculated on training speech activities: reading, writing, listening, and speaking; they also conta in explanation and repetition of a various grammatical material with corresponding tasks and exercises, as for independent training, and work in a group. If teacher can choose appropriate materials correctly necessary to pupils and use it in the form acces sible to pupils, both pupils and teacher will benefit a lot. Teacher can use lesson plans created independently, for example, on Power Point presentation. Children are involved in creative research process, as all projects are the individual-focused kind of work and as they write about themselves, their family, their house, and hobbies. By preparation of projects they study themes interesting to write, rummage in directories, talk to other people, search for photos and drawings even do audio and video recordings independently.

The list of used literature

1. Byrne, Don. Teaching Writing Skills. - Longman Group UK Limited, 1988.
2. Emig, J. Writing as a Mode of Learning // College Composition and Communication, 1977. - 28 (2).
3. Evans, V. Successful Writing. Intermediate Student’s Book. - Express Publishing, 2000.